

Section of the conference: Social Sciences | Sekcja konferencji: Nauki społeczne

How to cite: Torsu, L. A., Botsyoe, M., Agbodzi, G. K., Sokpoli, M., & Amegatsey, A. (2025). Relationship between Population Growth and Crime Rates. *International Conference on Next-Generation Innovations and Sustainability 2025*. Futurity Research Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15109897>

Relationship between Population Growth and Crime Rates

Leonard Atsu Torsu^{1*}, Mawutor Botsyoe², Gabriel Kwabla Agbodzi³, Michael Sokpoli⁴, Agbeko Amegatsey⁵

¹Department of Social Studies, University of Education, Winneba (UEW), Ghana, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5368-1159>

²Department of Business and Social Science Education, University of Cape Coast, Ghana, <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1752-8326>

^{1,3}Department of Social Studies, University of Education, Winneba (UEW), Ghana, <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-5419-5907>

⁴Dept. of Communication Instruction, School of Media and Communication Studies, UEW, Ghana, <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-9705-116X>

⁵Department of Educational Foundations (UEW), Ghana, <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6441-816X>

***Correspondence Author:** Leonard Torsu.

Accepted: March 14, 2025 | **Published:** March 30, 2025 | **Language:** English

Abstract: The relationship between population growth and crime rates has often been framed in a rigid linear or non-linear framework in traditional academic discourse. This study examined the relationship between population growth and crime rates in Kasoa, Ghana using Ghana Statistical Service data on population and crime reports from the Kasoa Divisional Headquarters over the years. In this study, we showed that the relationship between population growth and crime rates exhibits a dynamic and fluctuating pattern, indicating that this relationship is shaped by multifaceted socio-

economic and environmental factors. The result holds significance for crime prevention as one-size-fits-all crime prevention strategies and policies will be ineffective.

Keywords: population growth, crime rates, trends

Introduction

As cities grow, the demand for housing, employment, security and healthcare intensifies. This is often attributed to population growth in the cities which is characterized by high cost of living, resource shortages, intolerance among the less privilege, ultimately resulting in upsurge in crime (Mazorodze, 2020). Urban crime researchers have asserted that, growth in population as a result of urbanisation creates slums, unemployment, poverty and new forms of urban lifestyles that motivates the occurrence of crime (Owusu et al., 2016). Thus, one of the consequences of a growing population is more crime. Population growth refers to the increase in individuals (both natural and urbanization) in a population within a specific defined time scale. Population growth is thought to be a "multiplier" of all other factors. Studies conducted in North America, South America, EU, Asia and Africa, showed a strong correlation between urban expansion and rising crime levels. For instance, Rabbi (2024) showed that demographic stressors in the EU countries lead to increased organized crime and urban violence, which indicates that population expansion strains law enforcement.

The influence of population growth on criminal activities has been seen in many studies in Africa. According to Van-Dijk et al. (2021), Africa's crime rate has increased. Nigeria, Angola, Mozambique and Ghana have the highest scores in Africa. Adeyemi et al. (2020) used data from 2017 reported crime to conduct a spatial analysis of geographical patterns and risk variables of crimes in Nigeria. The study used statistics from Nigeria's National Bureau of Statistics to model six explanatory factors, including population density. Their method discovered locations of high population density that were also high in crime concentration, including all sorts of crime such as kidnapping, robbery, and theft. Forthwith, crime is assumed to be more common in more crowded locations, a statement that has typically been verified by cross-sectional research (Barton et al., 2025). Therefore, population increase tends to promote diverse types of crime.

Despite the significant linkage between population growth and crime reported above, it is important to note that crime levels across the globe seem to have diverging trends. Studies also prove that, larger populations are (occasionally) tied with less crime (Kubrin et al., 2024). This presents a bone of contention or divergent view in academic literature and needs further exploration especially with studies calling for more research (Lee & Jang, 2021).

Research Aim and Research Questions

Ghana's 1994 Population Policy admits that "the population of Ghana is the nation's most valuable resource. However, there have been growing concerns of crime hikes in urban and peri-urban areas such as Kasoa. The aim of the study is to examine the relationship between population growth and crime rates in Kasoa Township in Ghana. The research is to respond to the call by Lee and Jang (2021), who emphasized the need for additional research to test the relationship between population changes and crime changes. Specifically, the study answers the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between population growth and crime rates?

2. What is the trend of population growth in Kasoa Township over the years based on Ghana Statistical Service data?
3. What are the trends in crime rates in Kasoa Township according to crime reports from the Kasoa Divisional Headquarters?
4. What types of crime are most influenced by population growth in Kasoa Township?

We used Ghana Statistical Service data on population and crime reports from the Kasoa Divisional Headquarters to explore these questions. The statistical data on population rates were the population census data from the year 1970 to 2021 year. We then collected the available data on crime reports for various years. The available data were from the 2016 to year 2022.

Research Results

The following section presents and discusses the findings on the relationship between population growth and crime rates, the trend of population growth and crime rates and types of crime most influenced by population growth in Kasoa Township.

Figure 1

Trends in population growth and crime rates in Kasoa Township

Source: Authors' own development

In Figure 1, Kasoa's population has grown exponentially from 863 in 1970 to 236,527 in 2021. Over the past 30 years, between 1990 and 2020, the percentage grew even more when compared to the period from 2010 to 2021, where the population more than tripled. Kasoa has been described as one of the fastest-growing communities in West Africa. Its urbanization describes increased migration, possibly due to economic opportunities or job prospects. Trends in total reported common types of

crimes (2016–2022) varied greatly over the years, peaking in 2020 at 5,315 cases followed by slight decreases in 2021 (4,106 cases) and 2022 (3,694 cases).

The increase in crime rate between 2019 and 2020 could be associated with economic pressures from the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to joblessness and social distress. Therefore, the overall crime trend did not entirely mirror population growth. This suggests that there are socio-economic and environmental factors that contribute to the crime rate. Trends in specific crimes (2016 - 2022), including stealing cases, show a sharp rise in 2019, climbing to 238 in 2018 to 1512 in 2019 before gradually declining through 2022. Assault cases were relatively stable before surging in 2020 (1402 cases), but later declined in 2022. Fraud cases peaked in 2018 (736 cases) but declined in 2019 before fluctuating afterward.

All these could be attributed to economic conditions, possibly urban congestion, lack of social cohesion, lockdown restrictions, financial stress during the COVID-19 pandemic, improved law enforcement, or regulatory measures at different points in time. Although population growth is rapid, crime rates continue to fluctuate rather than steadily increase.

Conclusions

This paper examined the relationship between population growth and crime rates in Kasoa Township in Ghana. We used population and crime data to examine the trends. Population increased significantly and continued to increase which may have contributed to rising crime levels. However, crime trends continued to fluctuate indicating that the relationship between population growth and crime rate is context-dependent and not aligned to rigid linear or non-linear models. Kasoa's rapid urbanization contributed to a surge in property related crime such as stealing and fraud. Additionally economic downtime during the covid-19 in 2020 appear to have worsened criminal activities especially assault and stealing. As communities grapple with insecurity issues in rapidly urbanized regions, we recommend further studies to explore collectively, the role of law enforcement, community groups and personal protection strategies as the three most important pillars in crime prevention and control.

References

- Adeyemi, R. A., Mayaki, J., Zewotir, T. T., & Ramroop, S. (2020). Demography and Crime: A Spatial analysis of geographical patterns and risk factors of Crimes in Nigeria. *Spatial Statistics*, 100485. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spasta.2020.10048>
- Barton, M. S., Anderson, B., & Charles, C. (2025). Population growth and its paradox: An investigation into the correlates of four forms of violence in a rapidly expanding suburb. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 96, 102343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrimjus.2024.102343>
- Kubrin, C. E., Luo, X., & Hipp, J. R. (2024). Immigration and Crime: Is the Relationship Nonlinear? *The British Journal of Criminology*, azae045, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjc/zae045>.
- Lee, S., & Jang, C. (2021). Decomposing the Effect of Population Changes on Crime Changes. *International Journal of Advanced Culture Technology*, 9(1) 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.17703/IJACT.2021.9.1.1>

- Mazorodze, B. T. (2020) Youth unemployment and murder crimes in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa, *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 8, 1, 1799480, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2020.1799480>
- Owusu, G., Oteng-Ababio, M., Owusu, A. Y., & Wrigley-Asante, C. (2016). Can Poor Neighbourhoods be Correlated with Crime? Evidence from Urban Ghana. *Ghana Journal of Geography*, 8 (1), 11-31. <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/gjg/article/view/138515>
- Van-Dijk, J., Nieuwbeerta, P., & Joudo Larsen, J. (2021). Global Crime Patterns: An Analysis of Survey Data from 166 Countries Around the World, 2006-2019. *Journal of Quantitative Criminology*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10940-021-09501-0>